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DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSLATION COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN SPANISH LANGUAGE COURSES

ANNOTATION

In this article, one of the tasks of the educational process today is to teach students to be able to work independently in information and educational conditions, which are increasing every day, and to use information flows wisely. At the same time, this article is devoted to revealing the essence of translation competence. The article reveals the concept of translation competence, the importance of translation competence when teaching Spanish using interactive methods, especially the “shadow” method in modern education, as well as the level of its study based on domestic and foreign experience.

Key words: education, pedagogy, method, information technology, foreign language, distance education, methodology, system, translation, translator, translation, competence, translation competence, country, development, translation studies.

РАЗВИТИЕ ПЕРЕВОДЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ НА КУРСАХ ИСПАНСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье одной из задач образовательного процесса на сегодняшний день является научить студентов уметь самостоятельно работать в информационно-образовательных условиях, которые усложняются с каждым днем, и грамотно использовать информационные потоки. В то же время данная статья посвящена раскрытию сущности переводческой компетенции. В статье раскрывается понятие переводческой компетенции, важность переводческой компетенции при обучении испанскому языку с использованием интерактивных методов, особенно “теневого” метода в современном образовании, а также уровень ее изучения на основе отечественного и зарубежного опыта.

Ключевые слова: образование, педагогика, методика, информационные технологии, иностранный язык, дистанционное образование, методология, система, перевод, переводчица, переводческая компетенция, переводческая компетентность перевода, страна, развитие, переводоведение.

ИСПАН ТИЛИ КУРСЛАРИДА ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ТАРЖИМА КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯСИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада бугунги кунда ўқув жараёнининг вазифаларидан бири талабаларни кундан-кунга мураккаблашиб бораётган ахборот ва таълим шароитида мустақил ишлашга ва ахборот оқимларидан оқилона фойдаланишга ўргатишдир. Шу билан бирга, ушбу мақола таржима компетенциясининг моҳиятини очишга бағишланган. Мақолада таржима компетенцияси тушунчаси, интерфаол усуллардан фойдаланган ҳолда испан тилини ўқитишда таржима компетенциясининг аҳамияти, айниқса замонавий таълимда "соя" усули, шунингдек, маҳаллий ва хорижий тажрибага асосланган ҳолда уни ўрганиш даражаси очиб берилган.

Калит сўзлар: таълим, педагогика, методика, ахборот технологиялари, чет тили, масофавий таълим, методика, тизим, таржима, таржимон, таржима компетенцияси, таржима компетенцияси, мамлакат, ривожланиш, таржимашунослик.

Learning interactive methods of teaching is a special form of organizing communicative activities, in which learners are actively involved in the learning process, they have the opportunity to understand and think about what they are learning. In interactive lessons, the teacher's role is partly to direct the students' activities towards the achievement of the lesson goals [1, P.4].

Today, the demand for professionals who know foreign languages well in various fields is increasing day by day. This requires foreign language specialists trained in philological higher education institutions to prepare their languages at the level of native speakers. In this regard, it is extremely important to develop all types of students' speech activities equally in teaching foreign languages, which creates the need to introduce integrated education in HEIs, to organize classes based on new modern innovative methods, and to introduce effective interactive methods into the educational process. is bringing However, due to some shortcomings in the educational process, there are also cases of failure to achieve the set goal. It should be said that, in most cases, only students who have completed practical experience in foreign countries have such a qualification.

Today, the introduction of innovative technologies in language education on a large scale has become one of the urgent tasks. In particular, D.Bespalko, A. Kushner, K.Rodgers, L.Kamensky, I.Pestalossi, J.Yuldoshev advanced pedagogical technology, innovation, information technology and the requirements of the human factor in it are aimed at moving the results of the pedagogical system to the effective direction, even if only a little, and the current 50- from 60% (the maximum result of the pedagogical system) to at least 5-10% [2, P.82].

At this point, we think it is necessary to dwell on the explanation of the terms method, style and method. In the educational process, "method" is a procedure for learning or implementing something, event, process, and "method" is a set of methods that should be used to learn or implement something, event, process [3, P.98].

I.Rakhmanov and M. Berman say that "method" is a way of education to the goal [4, P.38].

B.V. Belyaev understands the method of education as the method and way of imparting knowledge to students and the unity of students' educational activities in this process [5, P.338].

And didacts emphasize that the term "method" is the work method of the teacher and teacher in the way of acquiring knowledge, skills, and forming the worldview of teachers and creating opportunities for knowledge. J. Jalolov defines the term "method" as a set of methods and direction of education in education [6, P.17].

Therefore, another factor of the successful use of interactive methods in the educational process is the pre-design of a specific, integrated educational process, diagnosis of the level of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by students, and education. is to be able to predict the successful outcome of the goal in advance.

Interactive method - by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process, it serves to activate the learning of students and develop their personal qualities. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The main criteria of interactive education: conducting informal debates, the opportunity to freely describe and express the educational material, the number of lectures is small, but the number of seminars is large, the creation of opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large group, class team assignment, writing assignments and other methods, which are of special importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work. At this point, we have been learning through our experiences that the use of the “shadowing” method allows us to achieve the intended results faster in terms of the development of translation competence in students by using interactive methods in Spanish language classes [7, P.162].

Reversal is one of the most important methods in translator preparation. This method is used with headphones. In this method, it is usually learned to listen to a sentence in the mother tongue and translate it in the same mother tongue at the same time, and translate it back into a foreign language at a later stage. Listening and responding at the same time is a learned skill. Translators are not necessarily born with this ability. Interpreters who fail to do this develop bad habits. Verbatim translation is used in training for translators. It is divided into two. Phonemic (shadowing) return and phrase (phrasal) return [8, P.12].

Phonemic repetition is the repetition of each sound exactly as it is heard without waiting for the whole meaning or word. The second is paraphrasing, that is, the student repeats the speaker's speech from beginning to end. A consonant must be preceded by a return statement. This method is usually used to develop the ability to listen and speak at the same time. Phrase reversal is also useful to ensure that the translator is not falling behind.

This method is the best way to train a translator. The rate of return has been the subject of much research. The time lag affects the translation. The reverse technique is a technique used before translation. The process of returning a word after hearing it with a slight delay is called return. Interactive educational methods are often used simultaneously with various forms of training technologies. The use of these methods increases the activity of training participants and improves the effectiveness of education.

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